

MESS 0017

AFW 1.1 - The monitor image as a means to explicate the potential AFW¹; pixelation, distortion, and motion on the image as a 'reflection' of atomic mass-energy flexion.

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
October 2022

Best viewed at: <https://bit.ly/3Mr54KO>

ABSTRACT

In a previous MESSy paper, the author presented some testimonial evidence for the proposed Aether Flexion Wave. The testimony led to not a foundational basis, but at least a strong indication that 'something' is happening beyond what's been discussed, and it was not neutrinos, gravity waves, or static electricity. If it was scalar magnetic waves², there remains a need to find these as well. But if it is simply a wave within the now discovered (via vertical interferometer) Aether (not anatomically defined), then we need some philosophical and metaphysical definition or 'image' for it. This paper utilizes the monitor image - literally - to propose a method of looking at (and eventually mathematically defining/refining via an ORDA:INED standard³) the Aether, and these proposed Aether Flexion Waves.

Keywords: Aether - Uncertainty - Data Analytics - ORDA - Triple Plane Theory - Cosmic Rearrangement

1

https://www.academia.edu/87949952/MESS0012_The_Aether_Flexion_Wave_in_Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis_CRH

² https://www.academia.edu/8547496/Scalar_Magnetic_Waves_and_Qi_a_first_draft_of_a_hypothesis

³ https://www.academia.edu/87578071/MESS0007_MIMS_2_101_The_ORDA_Standard

The Monitor Image as a metaphor for the collapsed PPPC

The potentiality-probability-possibility-cloud⁴ is a collapsed 3D structure, enabling the third dimension to be represented by change-flux (experienced as time) in Tiple Plane Theory⁵. It is guided by a complex quantum electrodynamical model (Heisenberg Uncertainty⁶, etc.) of causality and probability principles, etc. Nevertheless, the mental image of this cloud, even prior to collapse to singular outcomes, is basically two dimensional.

Thinking about this, in discussion with colleague J. Kines, the question is “how can the [basically invisible] æther flexion wave be modeled in a way that would explain the effect upon atomic ME, as proposed/experienced?”

Kines-Careaga introduced then the monitor image approach:

Figure 1 - Fisheye and Pinch effects on Bliss background; credit: Windows/Gimp/author⁷

In the above image, the 3-dimensional data of the natural setting is captured in the 2-dimensional image; this is common. Nothing controversial about this process photographically or mathematically.

The visible layer of pixels makes up the atomic ME. The invisible layer of Aether is the assumed lens of the image; normally without distortion. There have been times, however, when the constant c changed value in

⁴ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/86922819/Structure_of_the_Uni_Multiverse_pre_EPEMC

⁶ <https://phys.org/news/2019-06-quantum-physics-heisenberg-uncertainty.html>

⁷ The author tried, very hard, to find the original fisheye and black hole screensaver, especially in video or download, and the internet has lost memory of this screensaver! Both Google and DuckDuckGo!

measurement, and rather than address this the commission in charge of SI units changed the definition of a meter! This is problematic because the distances we are studying are quite short. See the following table:

Table 1 - Extremely Short distances

Atom Size	Electron Size	Planck Length	Gravity Wave	Strings	K-Gurvature
10^{-10} m	2.81×10^{-15} m	1.6×10^{-35} m	10^{-18} m	Assumed 10^{-35} m	1.32×10^{-60} m

Figure 2 - Classic image but with waves, subtly applied; credit: same

Demonstrating the ripples (proposed) is difficult because we are talking about an extremely subtle ripple, potentially starting at 10^{-18} to 10^{-60} m.

As a Change Theory MIMS with \$\$Value

The finding of this flexion wave - if it exists as the author has seen clinically (potentially simple solar and lunar radiation waves, or meteorological) and in the testimony of MIMS0014⁸ - is probably dependent upon not mathematics, but complex electron microscopy.

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/87940630/MESS0014_Gravity_as_a_Newtonian_PEMF_Resonance_and_Conservation

This will probably be discovered if and only when we search for the Changes⁹, and create LIGO-like experiments with many more billions of \$\$USD (or eulium¹⁰ tokens?) with a bent towards not mere neutrino detection, but also these little ripples. Again, they need to be detecting ripples not only biologically, but in materials that are in isolated chambers, in vacuum, and with vertical interferometers in each chamber, with atomic clock calibration for simultaneous detection. Would the ripple affect the atomic clocks, too? Probably! And that is a useful fact.

Figure 3 - Could 'black holes' (super plasmoid-pinches) look like this in the Aether?; (gif) credit: Overthinking Relaxation¹¹

Conclusion

The author proposes that we a) advance the TPT with a better PEMD related definition for time¹², b) invest in Change Theory to c) detect and prove portions of Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis¹³ and various PEMF and PEMC related modified sciences (like HEP and electrogeology), and to d) detect, find, measure, and define the potential Aether Flexion Wave. The results of this experimentation and search might yield important data for the protection of aerospace, industrial, and social infrastructure, the behavior of people - particularly unstable individuals - and prevent CHAOS¹⁴ from generating the worst disasters. The author proposes a multi-deca-nm level (10^{-18} to 10^{-60} m) detection, with simultaneous in situ vacuum chamber detection with entangled atomic clocks, computationally detected with (hopefully) optic computers.

References

1. "MESS0017: AFW - Using Fisheye and Pinch lens to discern Pixelation Adaptation," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://docs.google.com/document/d/1aoVsf0ryXu3WM20kPxxd_90XcWcCzB4v9hnzGv9yxDg/edit
2. "MESS0012: The Aether Flexion Wave in Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis (CRH,)" Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87949952/MESS0012_The_Aether_Flexion_Wave_in_Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypotesis_CRH
3. "Scalar Magnetic Waves and Qi, a first draft of a hypothesis," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2014, https://www.academia.edu/8547496/Scalar_Magnetic_Waves_and_Qi_a_first_draft_of_a_hypothesis
4. "MESS0007 - MIMS 2.101: The ORDA Standard," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87578071/MESS0007_MIMS_2_101_The_ORDA_Standard

⁹ https://www.academia.edu/80123254/MIMS_2_2_5_1_Applying_Change_Theory

¹⁰ www.eulium.org

¹¹ Swirling Colors in Motion Screensaver

¹²

https://www.academia.edu/88245613/MESS0016_Newtonian_Mechanics_Kinetics_and_Sound_in_an_Electrodynamic_Model_or_creating_a_MOND2_on_the_basis_of_the_Force_for_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Dynamics_PEMD

¹³ https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis

¹⁴ https://www.academia.edu/84913012/MIMS_2_2_5_2_The_Five_forces_that_Influence_Life

5. "MIMS 2.2.1.1-3: The Threefold Sacred Sciences," Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1LcH2FypSjI27RZYI8NnxqtXiHq8Ub7KsFrcRIRJ3pRE/edit#heading=h.4w083fuxm8i3>
6. "Structure of the Uni-Multiverse; pre-EPEMC," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, https://www.academia.edu/86922819/Structure_of_the_Uni_Multiverse_pre_EPEMC
7. "Quantum physics experiment shows Heisenberg was right about uncertainty, in a certain sense," Phys.org,/ The Conversation, H. Wiseman, 2019, <https://phys.org/news/2019-06-quantum-physics-heisenberg-uncertainty.html>
8. "MESS0014 - Gravity as a Newtonian PEMF; Resonance and Conservation," Academia, f. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87940630/MESS0014_Gravity_as_a_Newtonian_PEMF_Resonance_and_Conservation
9. "MIMS 2.2.5.1 - Applying Change Theory," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/80123254/MIMS_2_2_5_1_Applying_Change_Theory
10. www.eulium.org (would not load)
11. "Swirling Colors in Motion Screensaver," Youtube, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w7LuvupUFno>
12. "MESS0016 - Newtonian Mechanics, Kinetics, and Sound in an Electrodynamics Model; or creating a MOND2 on the basis of the Force for Plasma-Electromagnetic Dynamics (PEMD)," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/88245613/MESS0016_Newtonian_Mechanics_Kinetics_and_Sound_in_an_Electrodynamics_Model_or_creating_a_MOND2_on_the_basis_of_the_Force_for_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Dynamics_PEMD
13. "Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis
14. "MIMS 2.2.5.2 - The Five "forces" that Influence Life," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/84913012/MIMS_2_2_5_2_The_Five_forces_that_Influence_Life